

Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for Automobile Dealers in China

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Wang, Yuchen

STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8336-6660>

Dr. Jennifer P. Pomperada

Faculty, STI West Negros University, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6317-2818>

Mylene A. Bautista

STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6801-8215>

Abstract:

This study examined the effectiveness of marketing strategies for automobile dealers in China, emphasizing the 4Ps: product, place, price, and promotion. Using a descriptive research design, data were collected from 100 respondents across first-, second-, and third-tier cities through stratified sampling. Findings indicate that most respondents were male, aged 44 and above, with lower educational attainment and less than 12 years of service. Marketing strategies related to product, place, and promotion were highly effective, while price strategies were moderately effective. Significant differences in product effectiveness were observed based on gender, whereas no significant differences were found in price, place, or promotion when grouped by demographic factors. Based on these findings, it is recommended that automobile dealers establish expert groups to develop and implement marketing strategies effectively. Training programs should be conducted to enhance sales personnel's understanding of the 4Ps. Additionally, disseminating study findings to automobile dealers and sales personnel can provide valuable insights into improving marketing strategies. Future researchers are encouraged to analyze this study's results and methodologies to inform their research on similar topics.

Keywords: Automobile dealers, effectiveness, marketing strategy

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Effective marketing strategies are essential for automobile dealerships to attract potential customers, differentiate themselves in a competitive market, and build customer loyalty. Since customers often lack brand awareness and product knowledge, they rely on dealerships to provide sufficient information for informed decision-making (Patty et al., 2021). Beyond targeting potential buyers, businesses must also ensure their offerings align with market needs (Ibarra et al., 2018). Additionally, word-of-mouth marketing plays a crucial role in influencing customer decisions, making it imperative for dealers to adopt strategic techniques that retain loyal customers while preventing dissatisfaction (Nasir et al., 2021).

Marketing strategy serves as a long-term, forward-looking plan aimed at understanding customer needs to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage (Alisa, 2022). As both traditional and emerging auto dealers face intense competition, especially with the rise of the energy vehicle market, selecting and implementing the right marketing strategies is more important than ever. The success of automobile dealerships largely depends on marketing effectiveness, and the 4Ps marketing strategy—product, price, promotion, and place—remains a vital framework for boosting sales volume and revenue.

After reading news and statistical reports from various media outlets, the researcher discovered that many car dealers urgently need efficient marketing strategies to increase sales volume or even survive the market with intense competition. This encourages her to conduct a study to ascertain the efficacy of car dealers' marketing strategies utilizing the 4Ps of the marketing mix to provide many car dealers with insightful recommendations. Finally, the information gained from the results of this study shall give guidance and insights about how to sell automobiles effectively to increase sales and profits, as well as expand the literature on successful marketing strategies for automobile dealerships.

Current State of Knowledge

This study is based on the 4Ps Marketing Strategy theory by Jerome McCarthy (1960), which encompasses product, price, promotion, and place (Abigail, 2023). According to Kate (2021), an effective marketing strategy outlines a company's direction for several years and requires a comprehensive assessment of the business and its environment to identify opportunities for competitive advantage. Kerr (2021) emphasized that the 4Ps framework optimizes the benefits of a balanced marketing mix, with the product aspect focusing on design, innovation, branding, and supporting elements such as warranties and guarantees to meet consumer needs.

Dawson (2021) examined the 4Ps of marketing from a managerial perspective, distinguishing between uncontrollable factors like market conditions and the marketing environment and controllable factors such as products, pricing, branding, advertising, and distribution channels. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) defined "place" as the distribution channels ensuring product availability and accessibility. Mason (2021) highlighted pricing strategies as a mix of factors like discounts, payment terms, and various pricing techniques, while promotional efforts are used to drive sales and consumer demand.

Shu Mingjun (2021) described dealers as independent business entities managing sales and services with minimal supplier restrictions. Xiao Peng (2021) highlighted the marketing mix as a combination of strategies that drive long-term enterprise growth while meeting public and social demands. Over time, the traditional 4Ps—product, price, place, and promotion—have expanded to include people, process, and physical evidence as essential marketing elements (Huang Chunjiao, 2023). Yuan Jiang (2022) emphasized that businesses use the 4Ps to understand customer needs, differentiate from competitors, and shape brand perception. Dai Xia (2023) further noted that the 4Ps, though fundamental to marketing, are influenced by internal and external business factors and interact dynamically within the market environment.

Harson (2022) analyzed Apple's marketing strategy using the 4P framework, highlighting the company's success in developing an advanced marketing system while emphasizing the need for continuous refinement. Similarly, Susan (2021) applied the 4P theory to Louis Vuitton, demonstrating its role in positioning light luxury products and targeting specific Chinese markets. Cillo (2022) emphasized that an effective 4P strategy should be periodically reviewed and adjusted as products evolve and target markets shift. In the automobile industry, De Hooge (2023) reported that the global vehicle market rebounded in 2023, reaching nearly 90 million units as supply shortages eased and manufacturers improved inventory management.

Huang Qin (2023) highlighted Volkswagen's marketing strategies to restore its brand image through video ads on YouTube, offering insights for automobile marketers. Similarly, Xie Zhen (2022) emphasized the importance of marketing strategies for new energy vehicles in the low-carbon economy, as they play a key role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and expanding market share. The 4Ps marketing strategy remains a crucial research focus, with Huang Yu (2023) demonstrating its impact on airline service optimization and Liu Manxin (2022) applying it to Thai tourism, stressing the need for quality improvement and government oversight. Additionally, Yuan Chenzhao (2024) examined the growing influence of new media on China's market economy, urging businesses to integrate new media technologies into marketing efforts to enhance product presentation and expand channels.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study was anchored on the 4P's Marketing Strategy theorized by Jerome Mc Carthy and was proposed in 1960. This study uses the traditional marketing mix, which refers to four broad marketing decision levels: product, price, promotion, and place (Abigail, 2023).

According to McCarthy, the goal of the four Ps of marketing is to optimize the advantages of a properly balanced marketing mix. The features of the actual goods or services and how they relate to the needs and desires of the end user are the focus of the product aspects of marketing.

Product design, new product innovation, and branding are all included in the product element. A product's scope typically encompasses auxiliary components like guarantees, warranties, and support (Kerr, 2021).

Promotion encompasses all advertising, sales promotion, and marketing communications, including public relations, trade shows, exhibitions, and promotional education. Its main goal is to deliver a message that will elicit customers' responses (Xiang Qian, 2021).

Regarding location, this describes how the product is delivered to the consumer; distribution networks and middlemen, like wholesalers and retailers, allow consumers to obtain goods and services quickly (Claire, 2021). Setting a price for a product, including any discounts, is known as price. It can include customer sacrifices to obtain a good or service, and the things traded for the product or service, such as time, effort, or attention (Borden, 2022).

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of marketing strategy effectiveness for automobile dealers in China for the Calendar Year 2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment; 2) the level of marketing strategy effectiveness for Automobile Dealers in the area of product, price, place and promotion; and 3) the significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness for automobile dealers when respondents are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology:

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study investigated the Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for Automobile Dealers in China. Considering the nature of the research, the researcher used a descriptive research design.

Based on the theory introduced by Kowalczyk (2014), the descriptive research design is a study design that depicts the participants accurately. It is all about describing the people who participated in the study, and it can be done using observation, case study, or survey. It also engages in fact-finding procedures, particularly in conditions and relationships that exist, practices that prevail, beliefs that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are being felt, or trends that are developing.

Based on the above analysis, it is reasonable and appropriate that the researcher used descriptive research design to analyze the effectiveness of the marketing strategy for automobile dealers in China.

Study Respondents

The study aimed to investigate the level of effectiveness of the 4Ps' marketing strategies for automobile dealers during the calendar year 2024. Based on the research characteristics, the researcher chose 100 automobile dealers in different cities in China as the study's respondents. These respondents vary in scale, location, average monthly sale volume, and average monthly sales revenue. That is to say, these respondents have different characteristics that can represent the characteristics of automobile dealers in China.

Instruments

In this study, the researcher employed a self-designed questionnaire, which can be divided into two parts. Part I mainly deals with the profile of the respondents. The chosen respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire that determined the study's four variables: product, price, place, and promotion. Part II aimed to determine the level of effectiveness of the marketing strategy for automobile dealers in four areas of the 4Ps: product, place, price, and promotion. There were 5-line items per area, which was twenty (20) items. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale, which contains the following scores: 5 – always; 4 – Often; 3 – Sometimes; 2 – rarely; and 1 – Almost never. It was subjected to validity (4.72-excellent) and reliability (0.83-acceptable). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the validity and reliability of the instruments had been identified, the researcher sent emails to the sales managers of respondents for permission to conduct the study and sent the questionnaire to them. The respondents' sales managers were assured of the confidentiality of the data. After the communication letters were approved, the researcher administered the questionnaires to the target respondents. The researcher instructed the respondents on how to complete the questionnaire objectively and honestly. After answering, the questionnaires were retrieved, compiled, and then tabulated. Computation was processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed based on the objectives stated in the study. The results were interpreted and analyzed considering the study's objectives and hypotheses.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1, used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the respondent's profile in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

Objective No. 2, used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of marketing strategy for automobile dealers in China in terms of place, price, product, and promotion.

Objective No. 3 used comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether there exists a significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness for automobile dealers in China when respondents are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Participants’ personal demographic information results were collected and were noted in the data capturing sheet. Informed consent via verbal communication was elicited with the respondents. They read and understood the provided information and can ask questions. Moreover, their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw without giving any reasons. The respondents were assured that there would be no risks of harm will experience before, during, or after participating in the research. The data and information used in the study were treated with strict confidentiality. No statement regarding the participant’s identity was disclosed unnecessarily in this study. After the data gathering, since there was no need, debriefing was not done by the researcher anymore, as cited in the Data Privacy Act.

Results and Discussion:

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 44 years old)	42	42.00
	Older (44 years old and above)	58	58.00
	Total	100	100
Sex	Male	65	65.00
	Female	35	35.00
	Total	100	100
Civil Status	Single	50	50
	Married	50	50
	Total	100	100
Length of Service	Shorter (less than 12 years)	67	67.00
	Longer (12 years and more)	33	33.00
	Total	100	100
Highest Attainment	Lower (Bachelors Degree)	62	62.00
	Higher (Masters Degree)	38	38.00
	Total	100	100

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age; 42% or 42 were younger, and 58% or 58 were older. In terms of sex, the male group garnered a numerical rating of 65% or 65 or 35% or 35 respondents belonged to the female counterpart; when civil status was taken as a variable, the single group garnered a numerical rating of 50 % or 50 and the married group accounted for the same percentage. When length of service was considered variable, the group with less than 12-year length of service garnered a numerical rating of 67 % or 67 respondents, while 33% or 33 belonged to the group with more than 12-year length of service. Most respondents belonged to the group with less than 12 years of service. When the highest educational attainment was considered a variable, the group with lower educational attainment, composed of bachelor level, garnered a numerical rating of 62 % or 62 respondents. In comparison, 38% or 38 completed a master's degree. The majority of the respondents belonged to the lower group in terms of highest educational attainment.

This implies that most of the respondents were older, primarily male, had an equal percentage in terms of civil status, had shorter experience, and had lower educational attainment.

Table 2
Level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Product

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Automobile dealers maintain a wide range of vehicle availability.	3.34	Moderate Level
2. Automobile dealers offer a variety of color choices for each vehicle model.	3.78	High Level
3. Automobile dealers provide various trim levels with distinct features and specs.	3.71	High Level
4. Automobile dealers allow customization options such as interior materials and technology packages.	3.38	Moderate Level
5. Automobile dealers provide superior after-sale service for product maintenance.	3.78	High Level
Overall Mean	3.60	High Level

Table 2 shows an overall mean score of 3.60, interpreted as “high level”.

Both item No. 2, “Automobile dealers offer a variety of color choices for each vehicle model,” and Item No.5, “Automobile dealers provide superior after-sale service about product maintenance,” obtained the highest mean score of 3.78, interpreted as a “high level” of effectiveness. This connotes that respondents think it is essential for automobile dealers to offer diversified products for potential buyers, and superior product maintenance service is also an indispensable part of products.

On the other hand, Item No.1, “Automobile dealers maintain a wide range of vehicle availability,” got the lowest mean score of 3.34, interpreted as a “moderate level” of effectiveness. This could mean that in respondents' opinions, potential automobile buyers do not care much about the vehicle availability of Automobile dealers when making a purchase choice.

This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that product diversification and maintenance service matter greatly in product areas (Liao Yurong, 2021). Also, according to Li Yue (2021), product maintenance service is provided to keep a product in good operating condition. If product dealers want to attract more potential consumers and grasp a larger market share, they should not ignore the importance of product maintenance services.

The result implies that automobile dealers can effectively use product-related marketing strategies to attract more potential buyers.

Table 3
Level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Price

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Automobile dealers implement standard discounts on vehicle purchases.	3.56	High Level
2. Automobile dealers offer bulk discount pricing for fleet buyers.	3.37	Moderate Level
3. Automobile dealers ensure a competitive pricing strategy	3.39	Moderate Level
4. Automobile dealers provide cash purchase incentives.	3.49	Moderate Level
5. Automobile dealers employ a tiered pricing structure.	3.37	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.44	Moderate Level

Table 3 shows an overall mean score of 3.44 regarding price, which was interpreted as a “moderate level.”

Item No.1, “Automobile dealers implements standard discounts on vehicle purchases,” obtained the highest mean score of 3.56, interpreted as a “high level” of effectiveness. This connotes that standard vehicle purchase discounts are attractive to potential automobile buyers.

On the other hand, the lowest score obtained by both item No.2, “Automobile dealers offer bulk discount pricing for fleet buyers.” and item No.5, “Automobile dealers employ tiered pricing structure,” obtained the lowest mean score of 3.37, interpreted as a “Moderate level” of effectiveness. This would imply that bulk discounts are not very effective because fewer fleet buyers are in the automobile market, considering the price of automobiles. The result also implies that Automobile dealers should think twice before implementing tiered pricing schemes and strategies.

A study conducted by Anderson (2022) in one of the American automobile markets noted that standard and single discounts are more effective than bulk discounts for automobile markets and potential buyers. Most automobile consumers are just single buyers and cannot use bulk discounts when buying automobiles.

The result implies that it is moderately effective for automobile dealers to use some price-related marketing strategies.

Table 4
Level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in Terms of Place

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Automobile dealers utilize diverse distribution channels.	3.83	High Level
2. Automobile dealers ensure a strategic location of showrooms	3.32	Moderate Level
3. Automobile dealers implement robust online sales platforms	3.38	Moderate Level
4. Automobile dealers establish a collaboration with fleet buyers.	3.53	High Level
5. Automobile dealers utilize mobile sales units.	3.51	High Level
Overall Mean	3.51	High Level

Table 4 shows an overall mean score of 3.51 regarding place, which was interpreted as a "high level."

Item No.1, "Automobile dealers utilize diverse distribution channels.", obtained the highest mean score of 3.83, interpreted as a "high level" of effectiveness. This connotes that more distribution channels mean more chances to reach potential buyers.

On the other hand, the lowest score obtained by Item No.2, "Automobile dealers ensures a strategic location of showrooms," with a mean score of 3.32, interpreted as a "moderate level" of effectiveness. This connotes that since some consumers will not go to the showrooms of automobile dealers, it is not as effective as diversified distribution channels.

According to the Study on Place and Marketing by Yang Yu (2023), distribution channels focus on making the best use of the network of organizations, including manufacturers, wholesalers, and retailers, that distribute goods or services to consumers. Automobile dealers should never ignore this powerful tool. Another study by Huang Ting (2022) mentioned that different kinds of dealers should make the best of "place" elements in marketing.

The result implies that automobile dealers find using place-related marketing strategies to enlarge market shares practical.

Table 5
Level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Promotion

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Automobile dealers targeted advertising campaigns through online platforms.	3.78	High Level
2. Automobile dealers engage in local and national auto shows, allowing dealers to showcase their vehicles	3.40	Moderate Level
3. Automobile car dealers collaborate with influencers or bloggers.	3.86	High Level
4. Automobile dealers implement email marketing campaigns.	3.76	High Level
5. Automobile dealers organize test drive events.	3.51	High Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level

Table 5 shows an overall mean score of 3.66 regarding promotion, which was interpreted as a "high level."

Item No. 3, "Automobile car dealers collaborate with influencers or bloggers," obtained the highest mean score of 3.86, interpreted as a "high level" of effectiveness. This connotes that different social media platforms are important promotion channels for automobile dealers, given that social media has become a part of people's daily lives.

On the other hand, the lowest score obtained by Item No.2, "Automobile dealers engage in local and national auto shows allows dealers to showcase their vehicles," with a mean score of 3.40, interpreted as a "moderate level" of effectiveness. This connotes that the influence of offline promotion activities is not as far-reaching as that of online promotions.

According to the study on Core Promotion Methods by Adele (2021), promotion (marketing) is one of the four marketing mix elements, comprising any marketing communication used to inform or persuade target audiences of the relative merits of a product, service, brand or issue with the booming of social media, online promotion plays a pivotal role in the marketing process.

The result implies that promotion is key to increasing sales volume for automobile dealers.

Table 6
Difference in the level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Product when respondents were grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	42	50.96	1198.500	0.889		Not Significant
	Older	58	50.16				
Sex	Male	65	45.03	781.000	0.009		Significant
	Female	35	60.66				
Civil Status	Single	50	50.85	1232.500	0.902	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	50	50.15				
Length of Service	Shorter	67	52.50	971.500	0.315		Not Significant
	Longer	33	46.44				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	62	50.17	1157.500	0.882		Not Significant
	Higher	38	51.04				

Table 6 shows that there are no significant differences in the level of effectiveness when respondents are grouped and compared according to age with a p-value of 0.889, civil status with a p-value of 0.902, length of service with a p-value of 0.315 and highest educational attainment with a p-value of 0.882 as computed p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that "there was no significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness when respondents grouped and compared according to age, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment" was accepted.

On the other hand, there are significant differences in the level of effectiveness of the product when respondents are grouped and compared according to sex, as the p-values of 0.009 are lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that states "there was no significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness when respondents grouped and compared according to sex was therefore accepted.

This result is consistent with the previous study by Carson (2021), which found that different genders have different opinions on the effectiveness of product-related marketing strategies. In addition, product-related marketing strategies are also very effective, and companies should spend time and money on them (Joe, 2023).

Table 7
Difference in the level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Price when respondents were grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	42	50.62	1213.000	0.969		Not Significant
	Older	58	50.41				
Sex	Male	65	49.25	1056.000	0.514		Not Significant
	Female	35	52.83				
Civil Status	Single	50	48.30	1140.000	0.401	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	50	52.70				
Length of Service	Shorter	67	51.81	1018.000	0.477		Not Significant
	Longer	33	47.85				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	62	50.65	1168.500	0.940		Not Significant
	Higher	38	50.25				

Table 7 shows that there are no significant differences in the level of effectiveness when respondents are grouped and compared according to age with a p-value of 0.9699, sex with a p-value of 0.514, civil status with a p-value of

0.401, length of service with a p-value of 0.477 and highest educational attainment with a p-value of 0.940 as computed p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that states "there was no significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness when respondents grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment" was therefore accepted.

The present study found no significant differences in the level of effectiveness in terms of price when grouped according to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment. This finding is consistent with previous research that found that regardless of the age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest education attainment of consumers, price is the major consideration for purchasing for potential buyers (Alisa, 2023).

Table 8
Difference in the level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Place when respondents were grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	42	51.08	1193.500	0.859	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	58	50.08				
Sex	Male	65	52.09	1034.000	0.439		
	Female	35	47.54				
Civil Status	Single	50	49.49	1199.500	0.719		
	Married	50	51.51				
Length of Service	Shorter	67	52.75	954.500	0.252		
	Longer	33	45.92				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	62	48.95	1082.000	0.481		
	Higher	38	53.03				

Table 8 shows that there are no significant differences in the level of effectiveness when respondents are grouped and compared according to age, with a p-value of 0.859; sex, with a p-value of 0.439; civil status, with a p-value of 0.719; length of service with a p-value of 0.252 and highest educational attainment with a p-value of 0.481 as computed p-value are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that states "there was no significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness when respondents grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment" was therefore accepted.

The present study found no significant differences in the level of effectiveness in terms of place when grouped according to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest education attainment. This finding is consistent with previous research by Wang Chen (2021) that found that place or marketing channel is an indispensable element of the marketing process. Whatever products companies sell, the place provides platforms for marketing campaigns.

Table 9
Difference in the level of Marketing Strategy Effectiveness for the Automobile Dealers in terms of Promotion when respondents were grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4	51.4	1177.50	0.76	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	2	49.8				
Sex	Male	6	52.2	1022.50	0.37		
	Female	5	47.2				
Civil Status	Single	5	47.9	1121.00	0.34		
	Married	0	53.0				
Length of Service	Shorter	6	52.0	1003.00	0.42		
	Longer	7	53.0				

Highest Educational Attainment	Longer	3	47.3				
		3	9				
	Lower	6	49.0	1085.50	4	0.48	
		2	1	0			Not Significant

Table 9 shows that there are no significant differences in the level of effectiveness when respondents are grouped and compared according to age, with a p-value of 0.763; sex, with a p-value of 0.376, civil status, with p- a value of 0.343; length service with p-value of 0.423 and highest educational attainment with a p-value of 0.484 as computed p-value are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that “there was no significant difference in the level of marketing strategy effectiveness when respondents grouped and compared according to age, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment” was accepted.

The present study found no significant differences in the level of effectiveness in terms of promotion when grouped according to age, sex, civil status, length of service, and highest education attainment. This finding is consistent with previous research by Edison (2022). Promotion is a kind of marketing communication used to make the offer known to potential customers and persuade them to investigate it further. Promotion elements include “advertising, public relations, direct selling, and sales promotions.” According to the researcher, a marketing strategy without promotion is bound to fail and lose.

Conclusions:

The study concludes that despite variations in age, gender, education, and experience, automobile sales personnel are competent in applying 4Ps marketing strategies. Marketing strategies related to product, place, and promotion are highly effective, while price strategies show only moderate effectiveness, indicating that price wars are less viable in the 21st century. Notably, perceptions of product-related strategies differ by gender. Based on these findings, it is recommended that automobile dealers optimize their marketing mix through expert-led planning, implementation, and evaluation. Gender differences should be considered in product strategy formulation, and sales personnel should receive training on marketing strategies, including social media promotion, to enhance sales. Additionally, adapting 4Ps strategies based on market conditions is advised. The researcher should disseminate findings to automobile dealers and make results available on academic platforms for broader impact. Future researchers are encouraged to study these findings and adopt relevant methodologies for further research on related topics.

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